

Students' Satisfaction With Meals In Category A & B Schools Under The Free Senior High School Program Policy In Accra, Ghana

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Abstract

Objective: The main purpose of this study was to compare students' satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy in Accra, Ghana.

Methods: A comparative study design was carried out with a sample size of 450 students in category A&B schools Category A (Presbyterian Boys SHS, and St. Thomas Aquinas SHS), Category B (Ghanata SHS and West African SHS). Simple random sampling technique was used during data collection. Structural equation model was used to analyze the significance difference of the objective of the study.

Results: According to the findings, 84% of the respondents at Presec revealed that they are not satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. On the contrary, 67% of students at Ghanata are satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. Results from WASS and Aquinas indicated that, 60% and 59% of students respectively are not satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. The model informed that the most influential variable for determining meal enjoyment was quantity as a 1.975 increase in meal quantity corresponded to a one unit increase in enjoyment of meal. The other important variables were school category and taste of meals which also had positive values of 0.37 and 0.044. These variables were significant according to the model as the significance was less than the p-value of 0.05.

Conclusion: The study concludes on investigating the challenges of integrating locally sourced, cost-effective food items might yield valuable information for ethical and community-supported meals under the free senior high school policy.

Keywords: Satisfaction, School, Meals, Senior High, Policy

Introduction

Ghana provides an unusual public health quandary due to the prevalence of several and usually coexisting nutritional burdens such as undernutrition, micronutrient deficiencies, and overweight or obesity. Estimates from Ghana's children and adolescents (5-18 years old) suggest a considerable occurrence of thinness (boys 9.0%, females 3.2%) and a concerning frequency of overweight (boys 6.3%, girls 15.1%) (1). Improving children's access to nutritional food while minimizing hazardous meals is crucial, as bad eating habits are a major source of malnutrition (2,3). Population-based interventions in the school food environment have the greatest potential to promote nutritional well-being since children and adolescents spend a large amount of time at school and eat meals and snacks on a daily basis.

Students' satisfaction with dinner service has a significant influence on their overall well-being as senior high school students. As a result, food service directors in second-cycle schools must be up to date on current trends in providing children with meals that meet basic nutritional requirements (4). Senior high school is the second cycle of education, following basic education. In Ghana, second cycle institutions are senior high or vocational/technical schools that provide boarding and non-boarding (day) choices (5). According to the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), organized boarding facilities provide healthy food, sanitary conditions, and a daily routine of personal care, sports and recreation, as well as study habits that students take with them to their own homes and families and into their adult lives (6).

According to Nur and colleagues, students in non-boarding institutions live with their parents or guardians and attend school for at least six hours per working day, whereas their peers in the boarding system are directly cared for and monitored by teachers who ensure their nutritional, emotional, academic, and physical well-being (5). Numerous studies have identified the link between nutrition and academic accomplishment as well as student conduct, yet authorities in Ghana's health and education sectors pay little attention to nutrition, despite widespread low academic performance in schools (7).

However, the majority of adolescents in impoverished countries enter adolescence undernourished or malnourished, making them more vulnerable to sickness, early death, and nutritional deficiencies (8). Some dietary practices are common among teens, placing them at risk of unhealthy eating: snacking, mostly on high-energy but low-nutrient goods; meal skipping, irregular eating patterns; and a high reliance on fast food for meals and snacks. Other prevalent eating habits among teens include dining out and consuming insufficient amounts of fruits and vegetables. As previously said, these youths are often in second-cycle institutions, and the majority of them have these unhealthy eating habits (5).

Boarding students may bring simple items such as gari, shito, sardines, and so on to enhance the school's three square meals. At this phase in the life cycle, what is consumed is largely influenced by peers, mass media, social and cultural standards, and a lack of nutrition understanding, while the influence of the family declines (9, 10, 11, 12, 13). This can lead to low-calorie diets that lack the majority of essential nutrients. Poppe and colleagues revealed that a poor diet affects academic performance, emphasizing the need of paying strict attention to student nutrition at second-cycle schools (14).

School feeding programmes are very context-specific, with services tailored to each group depending on demographics, geography, and other factors both within and outside of schools (15). This is why creating and executing school food programs involves several challenges (15). According to Gase and colleagues, in order to deliver a successful school feeding program, countries must first determine whether school feeding is the most effective program for reaching out to needy children in their respective countries, then identify program goals and outcomes, and finally assess the type of food served in schools (15).

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to compare students satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy in Accra, Ghana.

Hypothesis

H⁰: There is no significant difference between the students satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy.

H¹: There is a significant difference between the students satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy.

Materials and Methods

The study was a comparative study between two categories “A” schools namely: Presbyterian Senior High School and St. Thomas Aquinas School and two category “B” schools consisting of Ghanata Senior High School and West African Senior High School. Hence, all the primary information were solicited from these four (4) schools. Additionally, the study would have love to broaden the scope of this study by adding more schools or different categories of schools but due to resource and time constraints, the study was limited to the above-mentioned schools in the Greater Accra Region. For instance, the initial purpose of the study was to investigate the issue between category A and C schools however, it was difficult to get the consent of schools under category C hence the study settled for category B. Data was taken at a single point on a specific duration (October to November 2020).

Sampling

Yamane’s formula was used to calculate the suitable sample size for the study. Yamane’s formula was calculated using a confidence interval of 95% and a precision level (error) of 0.05 (16). The sample size resulted at 450 participants. A simple random sampling technique was used to ensure that each student had an equal chance of being selected for the study.

Sample Size Recruitment

1. Respondents (students) were selected from the Presbyterian Senior High School, St. Thomas Aquinas School, Ghanata Senior High School and West African Senior High School. After the approval from each institution administration
2. Respondents were asked if they could participate in a research study, those who agreed proceeded.
3. Respondents were asked whether they are students, those who were not, were thanked and told they could not participate.
4. Respondents, who are students, were proceeded to answer the questionnaire.

Data Collection

Field data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire. Data was collected in English Language and it was a self-structured questionnaire. Questionnaire was designed to answer the study objective. Data collection was done according to the American Psychological Association data collections guidelines and ensured complete anonymity of all data.

Data analysis

Errors were addressed on the day of data collection after checking the completed questionnaires for consistency and completeness. Prior to inputting the data into SPSS version 22, the data was cleaned, sorted, and coded. The sample population was described using descriptive statistics, which generated frequencies and percentages of the characteristics of respondents who participated in the study. The independent variable is satisfaction with school meals under the free senior high school program policy and dependent variables are students in category A&B schools. Using structural equation model to identify the significant differences on the objective of study.

Results

Specific Meals Served at Selected Schools

In the process of finding out specific meals served at the selected schools, it astonishingly emerged that all the schools use the same menu for breakfast, lunch and supper. However, St. Aquinas SHS is a Day school so they are only entitled to lunch under the school feeding programme. The other schools in the study are fed thrice. Information from the management at the School Feeding Authority revealed that the same menu was designed for all schools in the Greater Accra region irrespective of their categorization. Below is Table 1, which depicts the various meals serve at the various school.

Table 1. Specific Meals Served at Schools

DAYS	BREAKFAST	LUNCH	SUPPER
MONDAY	Hausa Kooko with bread/spread	Beans and gari	Can fish stew with boiled rice
TUESDAY	Tom Brown porridge with bread	Tuna, groundnut soup with boiled rice	Sardine, hot pepper with kenkey
WEDNESDAY	Drinking Chocolate with milk	Beans, Gari and fried plantain	Tuna stew with boiled rice
THURSDAY	Corn porridge with bread/milk	Shito, egg on Waakye	Canned fish, stew with kenkey
FRIDAY	Tom Brown porridge with bread	Tuna, Palm soup with boiled yam	Tuna stew with boiled rice
SATURDAY	Hausa Kooko bread spread	Shito, fried fish with waakye	Sardine, hot pepper with kenkey
SUNDAY	Drinking Chocolate with bread spread	Hot pepper, fried fish with kenkey	Chicken, stew with jollof rice.

Source: Data from the field, 2020

Objective Testing

Bar Chart 1: Summary of the level of Satisfaction of school meals in Category A&B

Source: Data from the field, 2020

Bar Chart 1 above; presents the level of satisfaction among students from the selected schools. Here the results are presented in percentages in order to avoid spurious conclusion that may arise from using the frequencies of the results since the sample size for each school differs.

From the figure, 84% of the respondents at Presec revealed that they are not satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. On the contrary, 67% of students at Ghanata are satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. Results from WASS and Aquinas indicated that, 60% and 59% of students respectively are not satisfied with the meals served at the dining hall. In brief, it is evident that with the exception Ghanata School, majority of students from the other three selected schools are not satisfied with the meals served at their respective dining halls.

Generalized Linear Model

A generalized linear model was ran on the data using the proportion of students who enjoyed meals as the response variable and category of school, proportion of students satisfied with meal quantity, proportion of students who thought meals had good taste, proportion of students who thought meals had good texture, proportion of students who thought meals had good colour, proportion of students who thought meals had good flavour, were the predictor variables. The results are shown below:

Table 2. General Linear Model

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test		
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.
			(Intercept)	-.707			
[SchoolCat=0]	.370	.0000	.370	.370	.	1	.000
[SchoolCat=1]	0 ^a
[Type=1]	.044	.0000	.044	.044	.	1	.000
[Type=2]	0 ^a
Quantity Sat	1.975	.0000	1.975	1.975	.	1	.000
Taste	0 ^a
Texture	0 ^a
Colour	0 ^a
Flavour	0 ^a
(Scale)	.000 ^b	.0000	.000	.000	.	.	.

Dependent Variable: Prop. of students who enjoyed the meal.

Model: (Intercept), School Cat, Type, Quantity Sat, Taste, Texture, Colour, Flavour

a. Set to zero because this parameter is redundant.

b. Maximum likelihood estimate.

Therefore, from Table 2, we derive a general linear model that looks like this:

$$y = -0.707\beta_0 + 0.370\beta_1 + 0.044\beta_3 + 1.975\beta_5$$

Where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 is the school category (category A or B), β_3 is the type of school (day or boarding), β_5 is the proportion of students satisfied with meal quantity. This implies the variables β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 representing proportion of students who thought meals had good taste, texture, colour and flavour respectively, are irrelevant to the model hence do not explain the enjoyment of meals by students.

The model informs us that the most influential variable for determining meal enjoyment was quantity as a 1.975 increase in meal quantity corresponded to a one-unit increase in enjoyment of meal. The other important variables were school category and taste of meals which also had positive values of 0.37 and 0.044. These variables were significant according to the model as the significance was less than the p-value of 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Unlike in the past, where the menu of food offered at second cycle institutions varies depending on the total amount of fees collected, the category of school, and other factors (17), the results of this current study revealed that the menu for schools under the free SHS policy is the same for all high schools in the same region or district. As a result, in the Greater Accra region, all category A and B schools serve the same meals. The administration of many of the selected institutions, including Presec, has raised worry about the present quality of rice used. They stated that prior to

the free SHS policy, the rice used was of excellent quality and tasted better than the present rice offered, and that the school fees contributed to the quality rice used earlier.

Specifically, the meals provided under the free SHS policy consist of Hausa kooko with bread/spread, Tom Brown porridge with bread, drinking chocolate with bread spread, and corn porridge with bread/milk for breakfast; while the lunch consists of beans, gari, and fried plantain; tuna, groundnut soup with boiled rice; shito, egg on waakye; tuna, palm soup with boiled yam; shito, fried fish with waakye; and hot pepper, fried fish with kenkey. Specific meals serve during supper are; Canned fish stew with boiled rice; Sardine, hot pepper with kenkey; Tuna stew with boiled rice; Canned fish, stew with kenkey; and Chicken stew and jollof rice. Apart from Ghana Secondary School, which is a category B school that has high level of satisfaction 67% over dissatisfaction (33%) over school meals. Majority of students from Presec, WASS, and Aquinas have expressed high dissatisfaction for the school meals serves at the dining hall. Therefore, in comparison the level of satisfaction is relatively higher in B schools compared to A schools.

The disparity between planned meals and supplied lunches highlights the need for stronger school lunch compliance and enforcement methods. Given the economic limits and the lack of defined procurement criteria, Ghana's ongoing efforts to construct a public food procurement and service strategy might be advantageous. Clearer food purchasing guidelines may assist to standardize meal quality across programs. These criteria should be practical, taking into account local market conditions and seasonal availability, so they may be used and applied throughout several districts. Furthermore, increasing the meal allocation above the current 1.2 Ghana cedis per child/per day could alleviate the financial barriers that prevent caterers from adhering to menu guidelines and allow them to include a broader range of food groups, particularly fruits and animal-sourced foods, which are currently underrepresented. Caterer training on dietary guidelines and cost-effective meal planning can improve compliance by providing regular monitoring, engagement, and financial support to ensure successful implementation (18).

Conclusion

This study looked at to compare students satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy in Accra, Ghana. The study was conducted among 450 students in category A&B schools (2 schools from each group). The result indicated significance was less than the p-value of 0.05; this indicates a strong evidence in favor of the fact that the alternative hypothesis is correct. There is a significant difference between students satisfaction with school meals in category A&B schools under the free senior high school program policy. The study concludes on investigating the challenges of integrating locally sourced, cost-effective food items might yield valuable information for ethical and community-supported meals under the free senior high school policy.

Author Contributions

Jemima Evelyn Nartey contributed to the study concept, design, data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation, drafting and final review of manuscript.

Conflict of Interest and Funding

The author declares there are no conflict of interest and funding.

Ethical approval and consent to Participate

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, 2013 and approved by the with ethical clearance number (.....) before data was collected from the participants. All study participants consented for participation in this study. There were no risks in this research and participation was voluntary with freedom to withdraw at any time

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